

PlasmaPy Infrastructure and Maintenance

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Project Summary

PlasmaPy is a community-developed open source Python package for plasma research and education. PlasmaPy contains functionality to represent information about particles in plasmas, calculate frequently needed plasma parameters and transport coefficients, determine plasma wave dispersion relations, analyze data from plasma diagnostics, and track particle motion in electromagnetic fields. PlasmaPy is used in heliophysics, astrophysics, laboratory plasma physics, high energy density physics, low temperature plasma science, and fusion energy sciences. The proposed effort will focus on the maintenance and growth of PlasmaPy. Specific activities include performing official releases of PlasmaPy, maintaining compatibility with other Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) packages and PlasmaPy's upstream dependencies, coordinating community-wide code development and educational activities, providing user and contributor support, providing tutorials (including at biannual PyHC summer schools), fixing newly reported bugs, updating package and continuous integration testing infrastructure, and expanding the use of type hint annotations and static type checking.

Scientific/Technical/Management Plan

Software or Enhancement to be Produced

PlasmaPy is an open source Python package for plasma research and education (PlasmaPy Community 2024). PlasmaPy provides core functionality needed by plasma students and scientists in heliophysics, astrophysics, laboratory plasma physics, high energy density physics (HEDP), and fusion energy sciences. The mission of the PlasmaPy project is to grow a fully open source software ecosystem for plasma research and education: a collection of scientific software packages that are developed together, work together, and co-evolve in the same environment.

The `plasmapy.particles` subpackage provides functional and object-oriented access to particle data. The `formulary` subpackage calculates a wide variety of fundamental plasma parameters, collision frequencies, and plasma transport coefficients. The `dispersion` subpackage provides analytical and numerical solutions to dispersion relations in different regimes that describe how waves propagate at different frequencies and angles with respect to the magnetic field. The `analysis` subpackage contains analysis techniques and focused tools applicable to experimental or simulation data, such as finding magnetic null points in a simulation and analyzing swept Langmuir probe data. The `diagnostics` subpackage contains integrated analysis tools for working with real or synthetic data from plasma diagnostics, such as optical Thomson scattering and charged particle radiography.

Each function in PlasmaPy has a docstring that follows the `numpydoc` standard. The docstrings include a description of what each function does, parameters to be supplied to it, and examples showing how it can be used. Docstrings for functions related to plasma concepts include educational notes on the underlying physics. Subpackages such as `particles` have comprehensive narrative documentation. The gallery of 31 example notebooks introduces how to use PlasmaPy along with associated plasma concepts. PlasmaPy's documentation is written in `reStructuredText`, built using `Sphinx`, and hosted on `Read the Docs`.¹ The documentation contains an extensive contributor guide that describes how to get ready to contribute, the code contribution workflow, coding best practices, writing/running tests, writing/building documentation, and ways to contribute beyond code.

PlasmaPy has an extensive test suite to ensure reliability and maintainability. PlasmaPy uses `pytest` as the primary test runner, while using the `nox` automation tool and `uv` to ensure that tests are run consistently across platforms (including as GitHub workflows). The tests are run for all

¹ PlasmaPy's documentation is hosted at: <https://docs.plasmapy.org>

supported versions of Python and for multiple operating systems. Doctests are enabled to ensure that docstring examples remain correct and up-to-date. Approximately 95% of lines of code in PlasmaPy are covered by at least one of the ~4400 tests. The continuous integration suite contains multiple additional checks that are run for each pull request. For example, the documentation undergoes a test build so that no Sphinx or reStructuredText errors are introduced in a pull request. Static type checking with mypy is used to find errors in the type hint annotations that are gradually being added to PlasmaPy.

We propose to perform a baseline of maintenance activities to sustain and support community contributions to PlasmaPy for the next three years. Specifically, we will:

- Provide contributor support by giving or arranging constructive code reviews, onboarding new maintainers, triaging issues and pull requests, and keeping the contributor guide up-to-date;
- Maintain compatibility with other Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC) packages and PlasmaPy's upstream dependencies;
- Prepare for and perform ~3 releases of PlasmaPy each year;
- Coordinate community-wide code development and educational activities via biweekly PlasmaPy/PyHC meetings, and GitHub issues/projects;
- Prepare for and provide virtual or in-person tutorials and updates on PlasmaPy, including at the biannual PyHC summer school, the spring/fall PyHC meetings, and for various undergraduate internship programs;
- Provide user support, such as by working directly with PlasmaPy users or making documentation improvements to answer user questions;
- Fix newly reported bugs and add tests to ensure that bugs do not get re-introduced;
- Update packaging, testing, and documentation infrastructure for consistency with emerging best practices and any new PyHC standards; and
- Expand usage of type hint annotations and static type checking to find errors, increase code readability, improve documentation, and enrich contributor experience.

Providing contributor support and onboarding new maintainers will be the highest priority to promote software sustainability by growing the PlasmaPy community. Expanding usage of type hint annotations will be the lowest priority because providing this task to new maintainers will allow them to learn more about PlasmaPy's functionality and architecture.

Scientific Utility

The heliosphere and planetary magnetospheres are predominantly composed of plasma, and thus plasma physics underpins almost all of heliophysics and space physics. The PyHC ecosystem

therefore cannot be complete without dedicated plasma physics functionality. PlasmaPy is the sole PyHC package to fill this role. PlasmaPy provides functionality for representing particles, calculating plasma parameters, calculating the dispersion relationships of plasma waves, representing common equilibria, and analyzing data from common plasma diagnostics. We anticipate that PlasmaPy will be expanded in the future to include a wide range of functionality related to particle distribution functions, waves, turbulence, shocks, simulations, particle acceleration, and plasma diagnostics used in the laboratory as well as on spacecraft.

General or Infrastructure Utility

The most broadly applicable subpackage of PlasmaPy is `plasmapy.particles`. This subpackage includes the `Particle` and `CustomParticle` classes to represent particles, and the `ParticleList` class to represent particle collections. All of these classes have attributes like mass and charge which are `Quantity` objects from `astropy.units`. The `@particle_input` decorator lets us convert particle-like arguments to functions into particle objects. The `IonizationState` and `IonizationStateCollection` classes are used to represent ionic fractions for different elements and isotopes in a plasma, which is useful for analyzing data for *in situ* composition measurements of solar wind plasma and performing non-equilibrium ionization modeling of coronal mass ejection plasma (DuPont et al. 2020, Wilson et al. 2022). The `particles` subpackage is used within the `fiasco` package, which is a Pythonic interface to the CHIANTI atomic database.

Method of Production

PlasmaPy is developed openly on GitHub.² We will continue to make use of GitHub issues, pull requests, projects, and discussions to coordinate code development activities. We will hold biweekly meetings that all members of the community are welcome to attend, and regularly attend and provide updates at PyHC meetings. PlasmaPy abides by the Contributor Covenant Code of Conduct.

The code contribution process is thoroughly described in the contributor guide in PlasmaPy’s documentation. To propose a change to PlasmaPy, a contributor forks the repository, creates a branch on their fork, and adds new features to the branch using `git add` and `git commit`. The contributor pushes the changes to GitHub and creates a pull request from their branch to PlasmaPy’s main branch, which triggers continuous integration checks that must pass before merging. The pull request undergoes code review by a project maintainer who provides constructive feedback to be addressed before merging. The “good first issue” label is added to issues on GitHub to indicate appropriateness for a first-time contributor.

²PlasmaPy’s GitHub repository is at: <https://github.com/PlasmaPy/PlasmaPy>

Current Status

PlasmaPy development and maintenance has been supported since 2019 by a \$2.4M collaborative award from the National Science Foundation to the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO), UCLA, Bryn Mawr College, and the University of Delaware. This award has supported PlasmaPy’s growth from a fledgling package into a mature project with a broad user base spanning multiple disciplines. This award is projected to be fully expended by mid-2025. No funding for PlasmaPy development and maintenance has been confirmed to be available after mid-2025, which may cause future contributions by the most active current PlasmaPy contributors to become unsustainable and eventually cease.

PyHC Standards Compliance

PlasmaPy is fully compliant with PyHC standards, and is committed to remain in full compliance. The PlasmaPy package can be installed with package managers like pip, conda, and uv. PlasmaPy releases are currently made ~3–4 times per year and are available via the Python Package Index (PyPI) and conda-forge. PlasmaPy is compatible with macOS, Linux, and Windows. PlasmaPy is developed openly using git and GitHub for version control. Code in PlasmaPy is formatted and linted with ruff, which is in alignment with the PEP 8 style guide. Multiple pre-commit hooks are used to ensure quality of code and documentation for every pull request. PlasmaPy is thoroughly documented, and all public-facing functions and classes have docstrings that follow the numpdoc standard (which is checked by several ruff linter rules). PlasmaPy has a thorough continuous integration test suite.

The biggest challenge that PyHC faces is fostering interoperability among packages in the ecosystem. This challenge is particularly difficult because most PyHC packages were developed independently and predate PyHC by several years. A subset of PyHC packages — including the PlasmaPy, the SunPy ecosystem, and fiasco — are growing a pocket of interoperability by leveraging Astropy. For example, PlasmaPy was designed from the beginning to be interoperable with astropy.units. Dr. Nicholas Murphy (PI) has represented PlasmaPy in PyHC since 2018, and has frequently advocated for improved interoperability in the PyHC ecosystem. Throughout this effort, we will communicate with PyHC package maintainers via the ongoing biweekly virtual meetings to find opportunities to improve interoperability. As time permits, we will work to improve interoperability between PlasmaPy and other PyHC packages.

Maintenance Need

PlasmaPy is used in **heliophysics** (Barnes et al. 2019, 2024; DuPont et al. 2020; Qudsi 2021; Maruca et al. 2021; Jara-Almonte et al. 2022; Raymond et al. 2022; Krämer et al. 2023; Polson et al. 2023; Johnson et al. 2023, 2024; Johnson 2024), **astrophysics** (Feinstein et al. 2022),

HEDP (Pliatskas Stylianidis et al. 2019, Heuer et al. 2022, Davies et al. 2022, Simpson et al. 2023, Foo et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2023, Chen et al. 2024, Pokornik et al. 2024, Pilgram et al. 2024, Daneshmand et al. 2024, Rigon et al. 2024, Eisenbach et al. 2025), **laboratory plasma physics** (A. Murphy et al. 2023, L. Murphy 2024, Creamer 2024), **low temperature plasmas** (Jubin et al. 2024), and **fusion energy sciences** (Kennedy & Salmonson 2023). PlasmaPy has been adopted most widely in heliophysics (thanks to participation in PyHC summer schools) and HEDP. PlasmaPy has had 150 contributors. PlasmaPy has been forked 343 times and starred 585 times on GitHub. Among PyHC packages, only SunPy has had more contributors, forks, and stars. The breadth of the user base indicates strong need for continued maintenance of PlasmaPy.

Allen Kummer provides an example of PlasmaPy usage in the heliophysics community: *Pulsar Space Systems LLC is a Space Weather company building instrumentation and applications to monitor and exploit the thermosphere state for terrestrial and space situational awareness. We are building plasma probes based on pulsed Langmuir and Swept Impedance probe theories to measure both plasma and neutral densities with plans to deploy these in an operational capacity throughout the thermosphere. We utilize the PlasmaPy library for instrument data reduction and analysis with plans to continue engaging in the PlasmaPy with future contributions.*

Archive and Dissemination Plan

PlasmaPy is released under the permissive BSD 3-clause license. Official releases of PlasmaPy are made available on PyPI for installation with pip or uv, and on conda-forge for installation with conda. PlasmaPy's repository contains a workflow that can be triggered to create a new issue with the release process and checklist. The release checklist includes code quality checks, running regular and comprehensive tests, triggering the release, and post-release tasks. Performing a release on GitHub triggers a workflow that uploads the release to PyPI. The release on PyPI triggers a pull request to PlasmaPy's conda-forge feedstock. Once this pull request is merged, the release becomes installable with conda. The release is uploaded to the PlasmaPy Community on Zenodo and assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make each version of the package citable (e.g., PlasmaPy Community 2024).

Need for Resources

We request support for Dr. Murphy to perform 305 hours per year of maintenance and educational activities for PlasmaPy. In the following table, we present a breakdown of tasks along with the expected time commitment based on the times needed to perform these tasks in previous years.

Task	Time commitment (hours per year)
Provide contributor support	60
Maintain compatibility with PyHC packages and dependencies	40
Prepare for and perform ~3 releases per year	20
Provide project management and community coordination	50
Prepare for and provide tutorials on PlasmaPy (with more time needed during years of the biennial PyHC summer school)	25–75
Provide user support	20
Fix newly reported bugs	20
Update packaging, testing, and documentation infrastructure	20
Expand usage of type hint annotations (during summer school off-years)	0–50

The Relationship to Other Areas

Plasma physics is essential to astrophysics because the vast majority of baryonic matter in the universe is plasma. PlasmaPy has applicability to a wide range of plasma astrophysics applications including but not limited to stellar atmospheres, winds, and activity; pulsar magnetospheres; cosmic rays; accretion disks; jets; interstellar and intergalactic media; and cosmology. PlasmaPy has been used to investigate data from laboratory astrophysics experiments by PlasmaPy contributors from UCLA’s Basic Plasma Science Facility and the Omega Laser Facility at the University of Rochester. Plasma physics is essential to advanced space propulsion systems such as Hall thrusters. PlasmaPy can be applied to plasma technology such as water purification (Foster 2017), plasma medicine (Fridman & Friedman 2012, Nicol 2020), and industrial process control (Wang 2023). The diagnostics subpackage is applicable to *in situ* sensors on space weather satellites. The need for PlasmaPy — or something like it — has been recognized in multiple high-level community reports for plasma science (APS DPP CPP 2020, NASEM 2021), fusion energy sciences (FESAC 2021), and HEDP (LaserNetUS 2023).

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Facilities and Equipment

The Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian (CfA) is a joint facility of Harvard University and the Smithsonian Institution (SI). The CfA combines the resources, staff, and research facilities of the Harvard College Observatory (HCO) and the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO). SAO's administrative office provides accounting and payroll services, facilities management, and compliance advice on sponsored projects.

SAO project participants will be provided with sufficient office space at the CfA's 60 Garden Street facility in Cambridge, Massachusetts. Dr. Murphy has access to a Linux laptop and workstation provided through the Solar & Stellar X-Ray Group (SSXG) at SAO. SAO project participants will have access to the Hydra high-performance computing (HPC) cluster at SI's Herndon Data Center. At the time of writing, Hydra consists of 93 compute nodes with a total of 5088 CPUs.

SAO project participants will have access to Harvard University's library system, which includes a large collection of books, journals, and online resources related to plasma science, heliophysics, fusion energy sciences, Python, and research software engineering.

Table of Personnel and Work Effort

Name	Role	Commitment (months per year)											
		Year 1			Year 2			Year 3			Sum		
		This Project		Other Funded Projects	This Project		Other Funded Projects	This Project		Other Funded Projects	This Project		Other Funded Projects
		NASA Support	Total		NASA Support	Total		NASA Support	Total		NASA Support	Total	
Nicholas Murphy	PI	2	2	0	2	2	0	2	2	0	6	6	0
TBD	Fund Manager	0.24	0.24	0	0.24	0.24	0	0.24	0.24	0	0.72	0.72	0
Sum of work effort:		2.24	2.24	0	2.24	2.24	0	2.24	2.24	0	6.72	6.72	0